

Multi-Stakeholders' Perspectives And Evaluation Of The Nutritional Impact Of School-Based Feeding Program

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Abstract

School-Based Feeding Programs (SBFPs) are recognized as one of the essential interventions which aim to improve children's health and well-being, which results in positive educational outcomes. However, the effectiveness of these programs still depends on its implementation, including the stakeholders' perceptions and active participation. Thus, this study aimed to determine the perspectives and evaluations of the school-based feeding program from multi-stakeholders. Convergence mixed-method research design was employed. The respondents involved ninety (91) multi-stakeholders (grade 7 students, teachers/administrators, and parents) directly engaged in the feeding program at Felipe G. Calderon Integrated School High School. Researcher-made survey questionnaire and interview guide were utilized as research instruments. Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, one-way ANOVA, and Pearson correlation coefficient, while Thematic Analysis was employed to examine qualitative data. The findings of the study revealed positive and consistent results on the program's effectiveness based on the multi-stakeholders' perspectives ($M = 4.45$, $SD = 0.417$) and evaluations results ($M = 4.53$, $SD = 0.381$), both interpreted as strongly agree. These were evident on the selection of beneficiaries, menu planning and preparation, feeding schedule, and source of funds as demonstrated by the quantitative and qualitative data. The study found a significant positive correlation between stakeholders' perspectives and evaluations ($r = 0.679$), indicating a strong relationship between these variables. Overall, these data addressed the gap in the localized data on the stakeholder-based evaluation of feeding programs and contributed empirical evidence to the field of education, particularly in strengthening stakeholder-informed implementation of the School-Based Feeding Program.

Keywords: *School-Based Feeding Program, Stakeholder Perspectives, Program Evaluation, Student Nutrition, Educational Outcomes, Feeding Implementation, Menu Planning, Beneficiary Selection, Parental Participation, School Health Program.*

INTRODUCTION

School feeding programs (SFPs) are among the most widely implemented educational and nutritional interventions designed to improve children's health, school participation, and academic performance. These programs provide meals or snacks to learners while they are in school, serving as an effective strategy to address hunger, malnutrition, and barriers to learning. Across various countries, including the United States, Japan, and the United Kingdom, school feeding initiatives have demonstrated positive outcomes in enhancing children's nutritional status, cognitive development, school attendance, and educational achievement. Research suggests that adequate nutrition significantly influences children's physical growth, cognitive functioning, and capacity to learn effectively in school (Agujar et al., 2020; Reyes & Abecia, n.d.).

In developing countries such as the Philippines, school feeding programs play a critical role in addressing malnutrition among school-aged children. Food insecurity and inadequate access to nutritious meals continue to affect many learners, limiting their ability to participate actively in classroom activities and achieve optimal academic outcomes. In response to this challenge, the Department of Education (DepEd) implements the School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP), which aims to improve the nutritional status of undernourished learners through the provision of nutritious meals and complementary health interventions. The program seeks not only to reduce the prevalence of undernutrition but also to promote regular school attendance, enhance learner engagement, and support overall well-being.

At Felipe G. Calderon Integrated School, the School-Based Feeding Program has been consistently implemented to address the nutritional needs of learners, particularly those identified as severely wasted and wasted. Through collaborative efforts among school administrators, teachers, health personnel, parents, and community stakeholders, the program provides nutritious meals and monitors learners' nutritional progress throughout the school year. Home Economics teachers, in particular, contribute significantly to the implementation of the program by applying principles of food preparation, nutrition, meal planning, and food safety to ensure that meals meet learners' dietary requirements. Together with school health personnel, they help monitor and evaluate the nutritional condition of beneficiaries to support the achievement of the program's objectives.

Despite the recognized benefits of school-based feeding programs, their effectiveness extends beyond measurable nutritional outcomes. The success of such interventions is also influenced by how beneficiaries and stakeholders perceive and experience the program. Learners' perceptions of meal quality, program implementation, and overall satisfaction may affect their participation and engagement. Similarly, the perspectives of teachers, parents, and program implementers provide valuable insights into the strengths and challenges of the initiative. Understanding these experiences is essential for identifying areas for improvement and ensuring the sustainability and effectiveness of the program.

Although numerous studies have examined the impact of school feeding programs on nutritional and educational outcomes, limited research has explored the combined assessment of stakeholders' perceptions and the nutritional implications of the program within the context of

Felipe G. Calderon Integrated School. This gap highlights the need for a comprehensive evaluation that considers both objective health outcomes and subjective stakeholder experiences. Examining these dimensions can provide a more holistic understanding of the effectiveness of the School-Based Feeding Program and inform future policy and implementation strategies.

This study is anchored on the Hierarchy of Needs Theory developed by Abraham Maslow. The theory posits that individuals must first satisfy their basic physiological needs, such as food, water, and shelter, before progressing toward higher-level needs, including safety, belongingness, self-esteem, and self-actualization. Within the context of school-based feeding programs, the provision of nutritious meals addresses learners' fundamental physiological needs, thereby creating conditions that support their cognitive functioning, emotional well-being, social interaction, and academic development. By ensuring access to adequate nutrition, the program contributes to learners' sense of security, belonging, and self-worth, ultimately enabling them to maximize their educational potential.

Guided by Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory, this study seeks to evaluate the implementation of the School-Based Feeding Program at Felipe G. Calderon Integrated School by examining stakeholders' perceptions and its nutritional implications among Grade 7 learners. The findings of this study are expected to contribute to the enhancement of school feeding initiatives and provide evidence-based recommendations for improving program implementation and learner outcomes.

This study aimed to determine and explore the perspectives and evaluation of the school-based feeding program from the multi-stakeholders. The main goal was to collect valuable information that can be used to enhance the program continuously. More precisely, the study sought to address the following inquiries: (1) What are the perspectives of the multi-stakeholders on the nutritional impact of the school-based feeding program in terms of: (a) Selection of feeding beneficiaries, (b) Menu Planning and Preparation, (c) Feeding Schedule, and (d) 1.4. Source of Funds, as summarized using descriptive statistics (mean, frequency, and standard deviation)? (2) Are there significant differences in the perspectives of the multi-stakeholders on the nutritional impact of school-based feeding programs, as determined using Welch's ANOVA? (3) What is the evaluation of the multi-stakeholders on the nutritional impact of the school-based feeding program in terms of: (a) Selection of feeding beneficiaries, (b) Menu Planning and Preparation, (c) Feeding Schedule, (d) Source of Funds, as measured through descriptive statistics (mean, frequency, and standard deviation)? (4) Are there significant differences in the evaluations of the multi-stakeholders on the nutritional impact of school-based feeding programs, as analyzed using one-way ANOVA? (5) Is there a significant relationship between the multi-stakeholders' perspectives and evaluations of the nutritional impact of school-based feeding programs, as measured using the Spearman rank-order correlation coefficient? (6) What actionable strategies can be formulated to enhance the program's implementation, based on the multi-stakeholders' evaluations?

*Literature Review**Efficiency of School-Based Feeding Programs*

School-Based Feeding Programs (SBFPs) have been widely acknowledged as a critical intervention for enhancing the academic performance, health outcomes, and nutritional status of children. These initiatives are intended to mitigate starvation and encourage educational engagement by offering nutritious meals to students during their school days, thereby addressing nutritional deficiencies. School feeding initiatives are an effective social protection mechanism that contributes to both educational access and infant welfare, as per the World Food Programme (2020). Nevertheless, the efficacy of these interventions has been the subject of conflicting evidence in various contexts, despite their widespread implementation (Aurino et al., 2020).

The educational and nutritional outcomes of students have been positively impacted by school feeding programs, as evidenced by numerous studies. Appiah (2024) discovered that the implementation of school feeding programs in Ghana substantially enhanced student attendance and academic performance, while simultaneously reducing dropout rates caused by hunger and food insecurity. In the same vein, Lonzaga (2024) reported that school-based feeding initiatives had a positive impact on the academic achievement and nutritional status of students, with both parents and teachers regarding the intervention as effective. These results indicate that nutrition programs not only enhance the educational engagement of beneficiaries but also contribute to improved health conditions.

In addition to their pedagogical advantages, school feeding programs have been acknowledged as instruments of human capital development and social protection. Aurino et al. (2020) underscored that large-scale government-led nutrition programs produce equitable benefits, particularly for students from economically disadvantaged households. By increasing access to educational opportunities and decreasing disparities, these initiatives facilitate the attainment of global educational objectives. In the same vein, international organizations have emphasized the significance of strategic menu planning, nutritional adequacy, and sustainable funding mechanisms to guarantee the long-term efficacy of feeding interventions (Global Child Nutrition Foundation, 2021; UNICEF, 2023; U.S. Department of Agriculture, 2024).

Evidence indicates that the efficacy of nutrition programs may fluctuate contingent upon the context in which they are implemented and the design of the program, despite these favorable results. Muneza and Imaniriho (2025) reported that stakeholders have a positive attitude toward the educational and nutritional advantages of school feeding initiatives, particularly in terms of increasing classroom participation, concentration, and attendance. In contrast, Mostert (2021) contended that the influence of nutrition programs varies depending on the demographic and geographic context, suggesting that the outcomes of the programs may be influenced by community support, available resources, and implementation strategies. These discoveries emphasize the significance of assessing nutrition programs in the context of specific localities in order to ascertain their sustainability and efficacy.

Stakeholder Engagement and Perspectives in School-Based Feeding Programs

The successful implementation of school-based nutrition programs is widely recognized as a critical factor that requires stakeholder participation. Effective program planning, implementation, monitoring, and sustainability are facilitated by the participation of school administrators, instructors, parents, health personnel, and community members. Ferreira et al. (2019) underscored the necessity of continuous monitoring, strong stakeholder collaboration, and sufficient nutrition expertise to guarantee that program objectives are met in order to implement successful feeding programs. The study also underscored the significance of bolstering the role of school feeding committees in overseeing program operations and investing in nutrition education.

Additionally, research has demonstrated that programs may be rendered less effective due to inadequate stakeholder participation. Acheampong (2022) discovered that the implementation and monitoring of school nutrition programs were adversely affected by stakeholder exclusion, lack of awareness, and insufficient participation. Inadequate engagement may lead to inadequate resource allocation, ineffectual program supervision, and inadequate parental support, all of which can ultimately undermine the quality and sustainability of feeding services. These findings indicate that maintaining active stakeholder participation is crucial for optimizing program outcomes and guaranteeing long-term success.

In contrast, research has shown that learners' educational development and welfare are significantly influenced by positive stakeholder engagement. According to Gahite (2024), stakeholders perceived school nutrition programs as effective in enhancing students' academic performance, attendance, and overall well-being. Cubio (2025) also observed significant enhancements in students' motivation, energy levels, and school participation as a result of the implementation of nutrition programs in Tandag City. Parental practices and community support have been emphasized in other studies as factors that reinforce the nutritional advantages of school feeding initiatives (Caagbay & Luzano, 2023). These results suggest that the efficacy of school nutrition interventions is significantly influenced by stakeholder perceptions and participation.

Nutritional Consequences of School-Based Feeding Programs

The physical growth, cognitive development, and overall well-being of children are significantly influenced by their nutrition. Undernutrition continues to pose a substantial obstacle on a global scale and continues to influence economic development and educational outcomes. Childhood undernutrition continues to be a significant issue, as it has long-term repercussions on productivity, learning capacity, and health, as per the World Food Programme (2023). Consequently, nutritional interventions, including school feeding programs, have emerged as critical strategies for promoting healthy development and addressing malnutrition in school-aged children.

Research suggests that nutritional support during childhood has a substantial impact on developmental outcomes and growth. Chakrabarti et al. (2021) underscored the significance of

sustained nutritional investments throughout childhood, contending that interventions implemented during the primary school years can enhance earlier nutritional programs and mitigate the long-term consequences of stunting. School nutrition programs can enhance nutrient intake and promote healthy physical development among students by consistently providing balanced meals.

Additionally, classroom participation and cognitive functioning have been strengthened in correlation with improved nutritional status. Students are able to participate more actively in academic activities as a result of the support that adequate nutrition provides for memory retention, concentration, and learning preparedness. As a result, school feeding interventions not only address immediate nutritional deficiencies but also establish conducive conditions for enhanced educational performance and enduring development.

Educational Results of School-Based Feeding Programs

One of the primary goals of school-based nutrition programs is to enhance educational outcomes by overcoming hunger-related obstacles to learning. The World Food Programme (2020) identifies enhanced academic achievement, retention, and attendance as among the primary educational advantages of nutrition interventions. These programs contribute to the reduction of absenteeism and the increase in classroom participation by guaranteeing that learners receive nutritious meals during school hours.

Positive correlations between school nutrition programs and learner attendance have been consistently documented in research. Feeding interventions, particularly among learners from vulnerable households, are associated with increased enrollment and sustained school participation, as per the World Food Programme (2022). Complementary strategies, such as take-home food rations, further motivate families to ensure their children's school attendance by offering supplementary food security incentives.

School nutrition programs have a positive impact on the cognitive performance and academic achievement of learners, in addition to attendance. Obligado (2019) underscored the fact that students are able to perform better academically as a result of the fact that adequate nutrition improves their attention span, concentration, and learning capacity. Nevertheless, program implementation and educational outcomes are still impacted by challenges such as limited familial support, socioeconomic constraints, and accessibility issues, despite these benefits (UNICEF, 2020). These results indicate that, although nutrition programs offer substantial educational advantages, complementary interventions may be required to optimize their effectiveness.

Evaluation of School-Based Feeding Programs by Stakeholders

The experiences and evaluations of stakeholders who are directly involved in the implementation of school-based nutrition programs are frequently used to evaluate their effectiveness. Government agencies in the Philippines have consistently increased the scope of feeding initiatives to combat childhood malnutrition. According to the Department of Education

(2021), school feeding and milk supplementation initiatives have been beneficial to millions of learners, while the Department of Social Welfare and Development has implemented complementary feeding interventions for undernourished children. The government's dedication to enhancing infant nutrition and educational participation is evident in these initiatives.

The quality of the program is further enhanced by the implementation of evidence-based menu planning, nutritional standards, and financial support mechanisms. The development of nutritional menu guides and the promotion of culturally appropriate dishes have been identified as critical strategies for improving the effectiveness of feeding programs (Bumanglag et al., 2021; FAO, 2025). Similarly, the health and academic performance of students have been enhanced as a result of the sustained government funding and support from partner organizations (DBM, 2023; Caren et al., 2021).

School nutrition programs are typically praised in studies that analyze stakeholder evaluations. A broad consensus among stakeholders regarding the positive contributions of nutrition initiatives to learners' health and educational outcomes was reported by Takens et al. (2024). Nevertheless, there have been varying assessments. Galvan et al. (2023) discovered that parents tended to evaluate the significance and efficacy of feeding programs more favorably than instructors and nutrition experts. These discrepancies indicate that stakeholder evaluations may be influenced by their respective levels of involvement, expectations, and experiences with program implementation. As a result, it is imperative to investigate the perspectives of stakeholders in order to gain a thorough comprehension of the efficacy of the feeding program and to pinpoint areas for refinement.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a Convergent Mixed-Methods Research Design to comprehensively examine the perspectives and evaluations of multiple stakeholders regarding the nutritional impact of the School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP) among Grade 7 learners of Felipe G. Calderon Integrated School–High School. The convergent mixed-methods approach involves the concurrent collection of quantitative and qualitative data, separate analysis of each dataset, and integration of findings during the interpretation stage to develop a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon under investigation.

The utilization of this research design enabled the researcher to obtain both numerical and narrative evidence concerning the implementation and nutritional implications of the School-Based Feeding Program. Quantitative data provided measurable information regarding stakeholders' perspectives and evaluations, while qualitative data offered in-depth insights into their experiences, observations, and perceptions of the program. The combination of these two forms of evidence strengthened the validity of the findings by allowing the researcher to compare, corroborate, and enrich the results obtained from each methodological strand.

For the quantitative component, a researcher-developed survey questionnaire was administered to the identified stakeholders, including Grade 7 student beneficiaries, parents or

guardians, teachers, and school administrators. The instrument was designed to determine stakeholders' perspectives and evaluations regarding the implementation and nutritional impact of the School-Based Feeding Program in terms of beneficiary selection, menu planning and preparation, feeding schedule, and source of funds. Responses were gathered using a structured Likert-scale format to facilitate statistical analysis and interpretation.

Simultaneously, qualitative data were collected through semi-structured interviews using a researcher-developed interview guide. The interviews provided participants with opportunities to elaborate on their experiences, observations, and recommendations regarding the School-Based Feeding Program. This qualitative component enabled the researcher to explore contextual factors and gain a deeper understanding of issues that could not be fully captured through survey responses alone.

Following data collection, quantitative and qualitative datasets were analyzed independently using appropriate statistical and thematic analytical procedures. The results from both strands were subsequently integrated through narrative weaving and triangulation. Areas of convergence, complementarity, and divergence between the quantitative and qualitative findings were examined to generate a comprehensive interpretation of stakeholders' perspectives and evaluations regarding the nutritional impact of the School-Based Feeding Program. Through this process, the study was able to provide a richer and more holistic assessment of the program's effectiveness and implementation.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents who were actively involved in the implementation and utilization of the School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP) at Felipe G. Calderon Integrated School–High School were the respondents of this study. The stakeholders that were involved in the program were the Head Teacher, parents or guardians, school administrators, Technology and Livelihood Education–Home Economics (TLE–HE) instructors, and Grade 7 student beneficiaries.

The researcher was able to acquire a variety of perspectives on the nutritional impact and implementation of the School-Based Feeding Program as a result of the incorporation of multiple stakeholder groups. Firsthand accounts of their experiences and perceived benefits from the program were provided by student beneficiaries. Parents and custodians provided valuable perspectives on the program's impact on their children's academic performance and nutritional status. Conversely, educators and administrators provided professional assessments of the nutrition program's operational components, attendance, academic engagement, and learners' conduct.

Criteria for Inclusion

The following criteria were satisfied by participants in order to be enrolled in the study:

- Currently, Grade 7 learners are classified as Severely Wasted (SW) or Wasted (W) based on their Body Mass Index (BMI) records and are identified as beneficiaries of the School-Based Feeding Program.
- Guardians or parents of the students who have been identified as beneficiaries;

- School administrators who are directly involved in the planning, implementation, supervision, and monitoring of the nutrition program; and
- The School-Based Feeding Program is being actively monitored and implemented by TLE–Home Economics instructors.

Criteria for Exclusion

The following entities were prohibited from participating:

- Not beneficiaries of the School-Based Feeding Program, grade 7 students;
- Guardians or parents of learners who are not beneficiaries;
- School administrators who were not directly involved in the implementation of the nutrition program; and
- Teachers who did not actively engage in the nutrition program.

Population and Sampling Technique

The study population was comprised of ninety-one (91) stakeholders who were directly involved in the School-Based Feeding Program of Felipe G. Calderon Integrated School–High School. These comprised thirty (30) Grade 7 pupil beneficiaries, thirty (30) parents or guardians, thirty (30) teachers and school personnel who were involved in the program's implementation, and one (1) Head Teacher.

The study predominantly utilized total population sampling, in which all identified stakeholders who met the inclusion criteria were invited to participate in the study. In order to minimize sampling bias and obtain comprehensive information from all individuals directly connected to the School-Based Feeding Program, this sampling technique was chosen.

Purposive sampling was implemented as an alternative approach in cases where complete participation was not practicable due to the voluntary nature of the investigation. This method allowed the researcher to identify participants who possessed pertinent knowledge and experiences regarding the nutritional impact and implementation of the feeding program. The implementation of these sampling procedures guaranteed that the various stakeholder groups were adequately represented and facilitated the acquisition of both comprehensive quantitative data and rich qualitative insights.

Research Instruments

The study employed two research instruments: a semi-structured interview guide and a survey questionnaire that was devised by the researcher.

Quantitative data was primarily collected through the survey questionnaire. It was divided into three sections. The demographic profile of the respondents was acquired in the initial section. The second section assessed the nutritional impact of the School-Based Feeding Program from the perspective of stakeholders, including beneficiary selection, menu planning and preparation, feeding schedule, and source of funding. The implementation of the nutrition

program was evaluated by stakeholders using the same dimensions in the third section. The respondents' level of agreement with each statement was assessed using a five-point Likert scale.

In order to augment the quantitative findings, a semi-structured interview protocol was devised to collect qualitative data. The guide was composed of open-ended queries that were intended to investigate the experiences, perceptions, evaluations, and recommendations of stakeholders in relation to the School-Based Feeding Program. The interviews afforded participants the chance to elaborate on topics that were not adequately addressed in the survey questionnaire, thereby enhancing the study's overall findings.

The objectives of the study and pertinent literature on nutrition, stakeholder evaluation, and school-based feeding programs served as the foundation for the development of both evaluation instruments.

Validity and Reliability

The survey questionnaire and interview guide were subjected to expert validation by four professionals with specialized knowledge in education, educational research, and food and nutrition in order to guarantee the validity of the research instruments. In relation to the objectives of the study, their recommendations were directed toward enhancing the lucidity, relevance, organization, and appropriateness of the items. Based on their feedback and recommendations, necessary modifications were implemented.

The jury of validators was composed of a Science Research Specialist I from the Department of Science and Technology–Food and Nutrition Research Institute (DOST-FNRI), two Master Teachers from Mariano Marcos Memorial High School, and an Assistant Professor V from Colegio de Montalban. The instruments were refined as a result of their evaluations, which also guaranteed that the research objectives and the data collection tools were in alignment.

A pilot test was subsequently conducted among ten (10) respondents who possessed characteristics comparable to those of the actual participants but were excluded from the main study. Pilot testing was conducted to ascertain the internal consistency and reliability of the survey questionnaire.

Cronbach's alpha coefficients of 0.976 were obtained for pupil respondents, 0.969 for parents, and 0.977 for administrators and teachers, as a result of the reliability testing. These values suggest that the questionnaire items were suitable for use in the actual study and that they reliably measured the intended constructs, indicating outstanding internal consistency.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher obtained the requisite permissions to conduct the study and secured approval from the school administration prior to data collection. The research instruments were pilot-tested, revised, and validated to guarantee their appropriateness for data collection.

With the assistance of school administrators and personnel involved in the School-Based Feeding Program, eligible participants were identified on the basis of approval. Adult participants were provided with informed consent forms, and student respondents were required to obtain parental consent and learner assent prior to their participation in the study.

Quantitative and qualitative data were collected concurrently following the consent procedure. Survey questionnaires were distributed to the designated respondents in order to collect data on their perspectives and assessments of the nutritional impact of the School-Based Feeding Program. Simultaneously, semi-structured interviews were conducted with selected participants who represented the various stakeholder groups. In order to guarantee the privacy and comfort of participants, interviews were scheduled at mutually convenient times and locations.

Survey questionnaires that were fully completed were collected, verified for accuracy, and entered into the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) for analysis. Audio recordings of interview sessions were made with the consent of the participants and subsequently transcribed verbatim. All data that was collected was meticulously organized, securely stored, and handled with the utmost confidentiality throughout the course of the investigation.

Quantitative and qualitative data were independently analyzed following the conclusion of data collection. The narrative weaving and triangulation techniques were employed to integrate the results from both datasets, thereby facilitating the development of a comprehensive comprehension of the perspectives and evaluations of stakeholders with respect to the nutritional impact of the School-Based Feeding Program.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Perspectives of the Multi-Stakeholders on the Nutritional Impact of the School-Based Feeding Program

Table 1

Summary of the Perspectives of the Multi-Stakeholders on the Nutritional Impact of the School-Based Feeding Program

Indicators	Students Mean (SD)	VI	Teachers/Admin Mean (SD)	VI	Parents Mean (SD)	VI
Selection of Feeding Beneficiaries	4.53 (0.61)	Strongly Agree	4.74 (0.27)	Strongly Agree	4.63 (0.44)	Strongly Agree
Menu Planning and Preparation	3.98 (0.71)	Agree	4.36 (0.43)	Strongly Agree	4.23 (0.49)	Strongly Agree
Feeding Schedule	4.30 (0.58)	Strongly Agree	4.51 (0.42)	Strongly Agree	4.50 (0.48)	Strongly Agree
Source of Funds	4.37 (0.57)	Strongly Agree	4.81 (0.26)	Strongly Agree	4.48 (0.70)	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00–1.80 Strongly Disagree; 1.81–2.60 Disagree; 2.61–3.40 Neutral; 3.41–4.20 Agree; 4.21–5.00 Strongly Agree.

The summary of the perspectives of the multi-stakeholders regarding the nutritional impact of the School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP) in terms of the selection of feeding beneficiaries, menu planning and preparation, feeding schedule, and source of funds is presented in Table 1. The results indicated that the implementation of the program was typically viewed favorably by all stakeholder groups. The selection of feeding beneficiaries ($M = 4.53$, $SD = 0.61$), feeding schedule ($M = 4.30$, $SD = 0.58$), and source of funds ($M = 4.37$, $SD = 0.57$) were all highly rated by students, while the menu planning and preparation component was also well-received ($M = 3.98$, $SD = 0.71$). Similarly, teachers and administrators expressed a strong consensus on all program dimensions, with the source of funds receiving the highest rating ($M = 4.81$, $SD = 0.26$), followed by the selection of feeding beneficiaries ($M = 4.74$, $SD = 0.27$), the feeding schedule ($M = 4.51$, $SD = 0.42$), and menu planning and preparation ($M = 4.36$, $SD = 0.43$). In the same vein, parents expressed their strong agreement with all indicators, with the exception of the selection of feeding beneficiaries ($M = 4.63$, $SD = 0.44$), the source of funds ($M = 4.48$, $SD = 0.70$), the feeding schedule ($M = 4.50$, $SD = 0.48$), and the menu planning and preparation ($M = 4.23$, $SD = 0.49$). These results indicated that stakeholders regarded the School-Based Feeding Program as effective in its implementation and responsive to the nutritional needs of learners.

The quantitative results were consistent with the qualitative findings. Participants emphasized that the program provided nutritious meals that contributed to learners' health improvement and that beneficiaries were appropriately selected because they authentically

required nutritional intervention. In addition, respondents observed that the meals were balanced, varied, and served at the appropriate time, which enabled students to maintain their vitality and concentration during class hours. Additionally, stakeholders acknowledged that adequate funding was crucial for maintain program implementation and enhancing the quality of food and nutritional services offered to beneficiaries. These results suggested that stakeholders perceived the School-Based Feeding Program as a critical support mechanism that facilitated the health and school participation of learners, in addition to serving as a nutritional intervention.

The results corroborated prior research that indicated that school-based feeding programs enhanced academic engagement, school participation, and nutritional outcomes among students. Appiah (2024) discovered that feeding programs had a positive impact on academic performance and attendance by reducing appetite and enhancing nutritional status. In the same vein, Lonzaga (2024) determined that school-based feeding initiatives improved the nutritional status of students and their academic performance. Additionally, Aurino et al. (2020) underscored that large-scale school nutrition programs were effective social protection interventions that foster equitable human capital development, particularly among disadvantaged learners. Consequently, the current results indicated that stakeholders acknowledged the School-Based Feeding Program as an effective approach to addressing nutritional deficiencies, while simultaneously promoting educational participation and learner well-being.

Thematic Summary

The positive perspectives of the stakeholders regarding the nutritional impact of the School-Based Feeding Program were elucidated by thematic analysis, which yielded four main themes:

- The program was believed to have effectively reached learners who genuinely required nutritional assistance by stakeholders, as evidenced by the appropriate identification of beneficiaries.
- Nutritious and Balanced Meals: Respondents emphasized the nutritional value, adequacy, and variety of the food served.
- Stakeholders underscored the significance of timely feeding implementation, asserting that learners' concentration, energy levels, and classroom participation were facilitated by appropriate feeding schedules.
- Respondents acknowledged the necessity of sustainable financial support in order to enhance and sustain program implementation. They also acknowledged the importance of consistent and adequate funding.

These themes collectively suggested that stakeholders regarded the School-Based Feeding Program as a valuable intervention that enhanced the nutritional status of learners and improved their overall educational well-being.

Significant Difference in the Perspectives of the Multi-Stakeholders on the Nutritional Impact of the School-Based Feeding Program

Table 2.1

Significant Difference in the Perspectives of the Multi-Stakeholders on the Nutritional Impact of the School-Based Feeding Program

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value	Interpretation
Respondents	1.443	2.000	0.722	4.998	.010	Significant
Residuals	14.005	55.037	0.254			

The multi-stakeholders' perspectives regarding the nutritional impact of the School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP) were significantly different, as illustrated in Table 2. Levene's Test was implemented to evaluate the assumption of homogeneity of variances prior to undertaking the analysis. The homogeneity assumption was violated ($p = .025$); consequently, Welch's Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was implemented as a more reliable alternative.

The statistically significant difference in the perspectives of the stakeholders regarding the nutritional impact of the School-Based Feeding Program was revealed by the results of Welch's ANOVA, $F(2, 55.037) = 4.998$, $p = .010$. The null hypothesis was denied due to the fact that the probability value obtained was less than the 0.05 level of significance. This discovery suggested that at least one stakeholder group held a substantially different perspective on the nutritional effects of the program than the others. As a result, the stakeholders did not possess a unified viewpoint on the efficacy and implementation of the School-Based Feeding Program.

The quantitative results were corroborated by the qualitative findings, which also provided additional insight into the observed discrepancies among stakeholder groups. Enhanced Nutrition and Academic Performance, Corrective Nutritional Intervention, and Reliable Support for Economically Disadvantaged Children were the three primary themes that emerged from the thematic analysis. The varying perspectives of stakeholders regarding the benefits and purpose of the School-Based Feeding Program were reflected in these themes.

The program was predominantly perceived by certain participants as a dependable support mechanism for learners from economically disadvantaged families. The program's consistent provision of nutritious meals to children who frequently lacked adequate food resources at home was emphasized by respondents. The program was perceived by others as an intervention that directly contributed to improved nutritional status and increased classroom participation. These stakeholders emphasized that learners' attentiveness, academic performance, and vitality levels improved as a result of their participation in the feeding program. In the interim, an additional group viewed the program as a corrective nutritional intervention that was intended to rectify specific nutritional deficiencies and return learners to a healthier nutritional state.

The results indicated that stakeholders assessed the School-Based Feeding Program from a variety of perspectives, depending on their prior experiences, responsibilities, and level of involvement in program implementation. Although the program's value was generally acknowledged by all groups, there were discrepancies in their assessment of the intervention's most critical components. The distinct roles of students, parents, instructors, and administrators in relation to the program likely reflected these variations in perception.

The findings of Gahite (2024) were corroborated by the results, which indicated that school-based nutrition programs had an impact on a variety of aspects of learner development,

such as academic performance, attendance, communication skills, and overall well-being. Variations in stakeholders' perspectives were inevitable due to their diverse observations of the program's results. In the same vein, Cubio (2025) discovered that stakeholders generally maintained favorable perceptions of school feeding programs as a result of the observed enhancements in learners' academic performance, attendance, motivation, and nutritional condition. These findings collectively indicated that stakeholders' evaluations were influenced by the specific outcomes they observed and experienced, despite their recognition of the positive contributions of the School-Based Feeding Program.

Table 2.2

Games–Howell Post Hoc Test on the Significant Difference in Stakeholders' Perspectives

Comparison	Mean Difference	SE	t	df	p-value	Interpretation
Student – Teacher/Admin	-0.310	0.100	-3.109	48.052	.009*	Significant
Student – Parent	-0.165	0.116	-1.426	57.629	.334	Not Significant
Teacher/Admin – Parent	0.145	0.094	1.540	50.379	.281	Not Significant

Significant at $p < .05$

The findings indicated a statistically significant discrepancy between the viewpoints of students and teachers/administrators ($p = .009$). Conversely, no substantial distinctions were identified between students and parents ($p = .334$) or between teachers/administrators and parents ($p = .281$). These results suggested that the substantial variation identified by Welch's ANOVA was predominantly due to the difference between student respondents and teacher-administrator respondents.

This result was further elucidated by the qualitative findings. The current feeding schedule was generally well-received by students, who believed that it was effectively implemented without disrupting classroom activities. In contrast, educators recommended that meals be served earlier in the day due to the fact that some students were reported to have arrived at school without having consumed breakfast. Teachers have indicated that hunger may have a detrimental impact on the concentration and classroom participation of students, which may require modifications to the feeding schedule. These divergent perspectives demonstrated how stakeholders' perceptions of program implementation were influenced by their experiences and obligations.

Sadag (2025)'s assertion that stakeholders' perceptions of the efficacy of school nutrition programs may differ based on their level of involvement and participation in program implementation was corroborated by the results. In the same vein, Caagbay and Luzano (2023) observed that the perception of school nutrition interventions by parents may be influenced by their feeding practices and experiences at home. Collectively, these results indicated that variations in stakeholder perspectives were indicative of personal experiences, responsibilities, and expectations with respect to the School-Based Feeding Program.

In general, the results indicated that the stakeholders' perspectives on the nutritional effects of the School-Based Feeding Program were significantly different. The significant difference was observed between students and teachers/administrators, suggesting that these groups held varying perspectives on specific aspects of program implementation. However, the program was generally perceived as beneficial by stakeholders in terms of addressing learners' nutritional requirements, improving their well-being, and supporting their educational participation, as evidenced by both quantitative and qualitative findings.

Evaluation of the Multi-Stakeholders on the Nutritional Impact of the School-Based Feeding Program

Table 3

Summary of the Evaluation of the Multi-Stakeholders on the Nutritional Impact of the School-Based Feeding Program

Dimension	Students Mean (SD)	VI	Teachers/Admin Mean (SD)	VI	Parents Mean (SD)	VI
Selection of Feeding Beneficiaries	4.57 (0.53)	Strongly Agree	4.51 (0.48)	Strongly Agree	4.58 (0.41)	Strongly Agree
Menu Planning and Preparation	4.49 (0.48)	Strongly Agree	4.62 (0.36)	Strongly Agree	4.66 (0.29)	Strongly Agree
Feeding Schedule	4.55 (0.46)	Strongly Agree	4.35 (0.41)	Strongly Agree	4.68 (0.32)	Strongly Agree
Source of Fund	4.53 (0.53)	Strongly Agree	4.19 (0.53)	Agree	4.55 (0.48)	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00–1.80 Strongly Disagree; 1.81–2.60 Disagree; 2.61–3.40 Neutral; 3.41–4.20 Agree; 4.21–5.00 Strongly Agree

The results indicated that the evaluations of the various stakeholder groups were exceedingly favorable. The program's dimensions were unanimously endorsed by the students, with a mean rating of 4.49 to 4.57. In the same vein, parents demonstrated robust agreement with all dimensions, with mean scores ranging from 4.55 to 4.68. Teachers and administrators also provided positive evaluations, with a high degree of agreement regarding the selection of feeding beneficiaries, menu planning and preparation, and feeding schedule. Nevertheless, the source of finance dimension achieved the lowest mean among teachers and administrators ($M = 4.19$, $SD = 0.53$), which corresponds to a "Agree" rating. These findings indicated that the School-Based Feeding Program was largely well-received by stakeholders, who acknowledged its effectiveness in meeting the nutritional requirements of students.

Menu planning and preparation and feeding schedule consistently received the highest ratings among stakeholder groups, among the dimensions that were evaluated. The nutritional quality of meals, adherence to food safety standards, adequacy of food supplies, and timely food preparation were all positively evaluated by the respondents. At the same time, stakeholders

recognized the significance of adhering to a consistent feeding schedule, which they emphasized as a means of enhancing the nutritional status of learners, fostering healthy eating habits, and ensuring ongoing participation in the program. These results suggested that stakeholders perceived the operational components of the feeding program as effective and responsive to the beneficiaries' requirements.

Additionally, administrators, instructors, students, and parents expressed their enthusiastic endorsement of beneficiary selection. Stakeholders were of the opinion that the beneficiaries were effectively identified based on their nutritional status and that the rationale behind the selection process was adequately communicated. Respondents also acknowledged the significance of ongoing surveillance of beneficiaries to guarantee that the program continued to be responsive to learners who required nutritional intervention. These results indicated that the beneficiary selection procedures implemented under the School-Based Feeding Program were fair, transparent, and effective.

The adequacy and sustainability of financial resources were a prevalent concern in qualitative responses, despite the fact that the source of fund dimension received favorable evaluations. Participants acknowledged that the current funding was generally adequate to support program implementation; however, they also underscored that additional financial support could further enhance feeding facilities, expand program coverage, and improve food quality. Respondents observed that beneficiaries would receive more nutritious meals and additional health-related resources as a result of increased funding. These observations indicated that stakeholders regarded financial sustainability as a critical factor in the long-term effectiveness of the feeding program.

The survey results were consistent with the qualitative findings. The program was consistently praised by participants for its ability to improve the nutritional well-being of undernourished learners and provide them with nutritious meals. Stakeholders underscored the significance of procuring sufficient funding to support program operations, ensuring proper food preparation, implementing a consistent feeding schedule, and maintaining food quality. Concurrently, respondents offered constructive suggestions, notably in relation to the potential for increased financial support to improve the implementation of the program and the palatability of the meals. These results indicated that stakeholders highly regarded the School-Based Feeding Program; however, they also identified opportunities for ongoing enhancement.

The results corroborated prior research that underscored the efficacy of school-based feeding programs in enhancing the nutritional outcomes and educational engagement of students. UNICEF (2023) emphasized the significance of nutritionally balanced and meticulously planned meals in the success of feeding interventions. In the same vein, the U.S. Department of Agriculture (2024) underscored the importance of structured meal programs in satisfying the nutritional needs of school-aged children. Additionally, the Sustainable Financing Initiative for School Health and Nutrition (2024) and the World Food Programme (2025) underscored the significance of strategic funding mechanisms and sustained financial support in guaranteeing the continuous operation and efficacy of school nutrition programs. Consequently, the results of the current study indicated that stakeholders regarded the School-Based Feeding Program as a

beneficial and effective intervention that made a substantial contribution to the nutritional improvement and overall well-being of students.

Thematic Synthesis

Four primary themes emerged from thematic analysis, which elucidated the stakeholders' favorable assessments of the School-Based Feeding Program:

- Stakeholders were of the opinion that the program effectively identified learners who authentically required nutritional support through fair and transparent beneficiary selection.
- Safe, Nutritious, and Balanced Meals: Respondents prioritized the nutritional value, adequacy, and quality of the meals provided.
- Enhanced Health Outcomes and Healthy Eating Habits: The Consistency of Feeding Schedule as a Driver of Nutritional Improvement was acknowledged by stakeholders.
- The significance of sustainable financial support was underscored by the participants, who emphasized the necessity of consistent and adequate funding to enhance and sustain the implementation of the program.

Collectively, these themes substantiated the quantitative findings and illustrated that stakeholders regarded the School-Based Feeding Program as an effective intervention for enhancing the health and well-being of learners and addressing nutritional deficiencies.

Significant Difference on the Evaluations of the Multi-Stakeholders on the Nutritional Impact of the School-Based Feeding Program

Table 4

Significant Differences in the Evaluations of the Multi-Stakeholders on the Nutritional Impact of the School-Based Feeding Program

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value	Interpretation
Respondents	0.647	2	0.324	2.254	0.111	Not Significant
Residuals	12.488	87	0.144			

The assumption of homogeneity of variances was verified through Levene's Test prior to the analysis' execution ($p = .609$). As a result, a one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was conducted to ascertain whether there were any substantial disparities among the assessments of the nutritional impact of the program by students, teachers/administrators, and parents.

$F(2, 87) = 2.254, p = .111$, the findings indicated that there was no statistically significant difference between the stakeholder groups' evaluations. The null hypothesis was adopted because the probability value obtained exceeded the 0.05 level of significance. This discovery suggested that the nutritional impact of the School-Based Feeding Program was evaluated in a similar manner by students, teachers/administrators, and parents. In general, the three groups evaluated the program's effectiveness in a similar manner, despite their various roles, responsibilities, and levels of involvement in program implementation.

The lack of a substantial difference indicated that stakeholders consistently acknowledged the program's role in enhancing the nutritional status of learners and promoting their overall well-being. A common perception that the program was effectively implemented and responsive to the nutritional requirements of its beneficiaries was reflected in the favorable evaluations obtained across the dimensions of beneficiary selection, menu planning and preparation, feeding schedule, and source of funds. This consistency in evaluation may be attributed to the stakeholders' shared observations of the program's outcomes, which include improvements in learners' nutritional status, participation in school activities, and access to nutritious meals.

The qualitative findings corroborated the quantitative results and illustrated the convergence of the stakeholder groups. The School-Based Feeding Program was consistently praised by participants for its effectiveness in meeting the nutritional requirements of students, particularly those who were economically disadvantaged and undernourished. Respondents underscored the significance of maintaining a consistent feeding schedule, ensuring food safety, providing nutritious meals, and ensuring that there is sufficient funding to support the implementation of the program. Despite the fact that stakeholders provided suggestions for further improvement, their responses collectively demonstrated gratification with the program and confidence in its ability to foster the health and nutritional development of learners.

The results were consistent with prior research that underscored the beneficial effects of school-based feeding programs on the educational and nutritional outcomes of students. According to Appiah (2024), nutrition interventions resulted in improved attendance, reduced hunger, and improved academic performance among beneficiaries. In the same vein, Lonzaga (2024) discovered that school-based feeding programs had a positive impact on the academic achievement and nutritional status of students, leading to favorable evaluations from both parents and instructors. Furthermore, Muneza and Imaniriho (2025) reported that the nutritional impact of school feeding programs was viewed favorably by stakeholders, particularly in terms of learners' attendance, concentration, and classroom performance. Therefore, the uniformity of the evaluations observed in the current study indicated that stakeholders acknowledged the value and efficacy of the School-Based Feeding Program as a nutritional intervention.

In general, the results indicated that the stakeholders maintained comparable assessments of the nutritional effects of the School-Based Feeding Program. The absence of statistically significant differences was indicative of a consensus among students, teachers/administrators, and parents regarding the program's efficacy in addressing learners' nutritional requirements and promoting their overall development. The program's credibility, acceptability, and perceived success within the school community may be indicated by the agreement among constituent groups.

Conclusion

This study examined the perspectives and evaluations of the multi-stakeholders (students, teachers/administrators, and parents) regarding the nutritional impact of the School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP). Consequently, the findings of the study revealed positive and consistent results on the program's effectiveness particularly on the selection of beneficiaries, menu planning and preparation, feeding schedule, and source of funds.

Hence, the use of mixed-method approach has enriched the data and abled the study to address the gap in the localized data on the stakeholder-based evaluation of feeding programs and contributed empirical evidence to the field of educational program evaluation and school health management, particularly in strengthening stakeholder-informed implementation of the School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP).

Furthermore, based on the Statement of the Problem, the following conclusions are drawn: (1) The School-Based Feeding Program is effective in supporting the nutritional needs of students. Its effectiveness is shown through the careful selection of beneficiaries, provision of balanced meals, proper meal scheduling that enhances students' focus and engagement, and consistent program implementation that sustains students' well-being. In addition, several themes emerged from the thematic analysis of the respondents' interview responses. Hence, although current funding adequately supports program operations, additional resources would further enhance its nutritional services and overall impact on students' health and academic performance. (2) There is a statistically significant difference in the perspectives of multi-stakeholders, particularly between students and teachers/administrators. This indicates variation in how these groups perceive the nutritional impact and implementation of the program. Furthermore, thematic analysis of the respondents' interview data revealed several key themes highlighting both the strengths and areas for improvement in the program's implementation. (3) Multi-stakeholders demonstrate a strong consensus regarding the effective implementation of the SBFP in improving students' nutrition. This consensus is reflected in the efficient execution of key processes, including beneficiary selection, menu planning, feeding schedules, and fund management. On the other hand, the thematic analysis of respondents' interviews further highlighted a number of significant themes. While minor concerns such as food palatability, inconsistent taste-testing, budget limitations, and the need for sustained consistency were identified, the program is positively evaluated in terms of organization, health impact, and overall implementation. (4) There is no statistically significant difference in the overall evaluations of multi-stakeholders regarding the nutritional impact of the SBFP. This indicates a generally uniform and positive assessment of the program's effectiveness across stakeholder groups. At the same time, analysis of the respondents' interviews revealed key thematic patterns that provide insight into the study's findings. (5) A strong and statistically significant positive correlation exists between stakeholders' perspectives and their evaluations of SBFP. More favorable perceptions of program implementation are associated with higher evaluations of its nutritional effectiveness. Thus, the analysis of interview data resulted in the emergence of multiple themes relevant to the study. (6) Formulation of mixed method table was done based on quantitative and qualitative data and how the proposed program will address identified needs were formulated aiming to enhance the implementation of the School-Based Feeding Program.

Recommendations

On the basis of the study's outcomes, the following recommendations are formed: (a) Conduct height and weight measurements twice (pre- and post-validation) and establish a Beneficiary Validation Committee. (b) Align weekly menus with age-appropriate caloric and nutrient requirements following Department of Education and DOST-FNRI guidelines and Adjust portions according to age, appetite, and nutritional status. (c) Implement a standard feeding routine and prepare backup meal provisions (e.g., pre-packed meals). (d) Allocate

additional resources to enhance meal quality and monitor program reach and equity. (e) Conduct home visits, socio-economic assessments, and consultations and regularly update beneficiary lists based on changes in students' socio-economic or nutritional status. (f) Conduct proper culinary/cookery workshops for the SBFP cooks and implement periodic menu testing and feedback. (g) 7. Allow minor schedule adjustments when necessary to accommodate learning activities or special events while maintaining consistency and track alertness, engagement, and food intake to evaluate the impact of any changes on student wellbeing and learning. (h) Expand the program reach and collaborate with local farmers and suppliers which may reduce procurement costs while supporting local economies.

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